

Management

TIME MANAGEMENT AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT OF HIGHER SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract

Time Management is a set of principles, practices, skill, tool and systems that work together to help us to get more value out of our his/her time with the aim of improving the quality of our life. The most appropriate word which suites Time Management is self-management which helps us to keep stress to a maximum. Time is the scarcest resource and unless its management decides the success or the failure of an activity. Effective Time Management necessitates a sense of balance. Either extreme along the Time Management skill continuum can be problematic. On one hand, perfect Time Management skill do not make one a perfect student or employee. It is possible to excess time, such that one is so wrapped up in the minutiae that meaningful tasks are not accomplished. On the other hand, poor Time Management skill do not make one a stooge. Some brilliant peoples habitually are ‘a day late and a dollar short’. The main reason for managing time is just provide structure to one’s life and in turn, peace of mind. Managing time is just something one does for one’s own psyche, to make one’s days easier. It is important for a student to have effective strategies to manage his time to balance the conflicting demands of time for the study. Time Management skills are valuable for doing revision for examinations. Sometimes it may seem that there is not enough time to do everything that we need to. This can lead to a buildup of stress. When revising for examinations or during our final year when we have to combine the pressures of intensive study with finding time to apply for our task good management of our time can be particularly important. Once we have identification ways in which we can improve the management of our time, we can begin to adjust our routines and patterns of behaviour to reduce any time-related stress in our lives. Keeping this in view the paper has been prepared on some of the significance of Time Management and Academic Achievement of School Students.

Keywords: Time Management; Academic Achievement; School Students.

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1. Introduction

Time Management is the act or process of exercising conscious control over the amount of time spent on specific activities, especially to increase efficiency or productivity. Time Management may be aided by a range of skills, tools and techniques used to manage time when accomplishing specific tasks, projects and goals. This set encompasses a wide scope of activities and these include planning, allocating, setting goals, delegation, analysis of time spent, monitoring, organizing, scheduling and prioritizing. Initially, Time Management referred to just business or work activities, but eventually the term broadened to include personal activities as well. A Time Management system is a designed combination of processes, tools, techniques and methods. Usually, Time Management is a necessity in any project development as it determines the project completion time and scope.

Good Time Management is essential if us to handle a heavy workload without excessive stress. By using Time Management skill effectively, we can reduce work stress by being more in control of our time, by being more productive. This ensures that us to relax outside work. The central shift of attitude with in Time Management is to concentrate on results, not on activity.

Time is a resource that must be managed in a forward-looking way. It is not like money that one can put in a bank and use at a later time. One must be prepared to use it when the available time arrives. Planning is very important in managing: learning to manage time to get the work done at the level of that one desires is an essential skill to learn to be productive and satisfying while allowing time for other important activities with family, friends or simply to pursue own.

Time Management is not doing the wrong things quicker; it is doing the right things. Time Management refers to the development of processes and tool that increase efficiency and productivity. Human lives are made of seven vital areas; Health, Family, Financial, Intellectual, Social, Professional and Spiritual. If in the long run, individuals spend a sufficient quantity and quality of time in each area, their lives will be in balance. But if they neglect any one area, never mind two or three, they will eventually sabotage their success. If they do not take time for health, their family life and social life are hurt. If one's financial area is out of balance, one will not be able to focus adequately on one's intellectual goals. Also, working with a clean environment gives the focus needed to become successful.

2. Time Management

Time Management is a set of principles, practices, skill, tool and systems that work together to help us to get more value out of our his/her time with the aim of improving the quality of our life. The most appropriate word which suites Time Management is self-management which helps us to keep stress to a maximum. Time is the scarcest resource and unless its management decides the success or the failure of an activity.

Effective Time Management necessitates a sense of balance. Either extreme along the Time Management skill continuum can be problematic. On one hand, perfect Time Management skill do not make one a perfect student or employee. It is possible to excess time, such that one is so wrapped up in the minutiae (precious details) that meaningful tasks are not accomplished. On the

other hand, poor Time Management skill do not make one a stooge. Some brilliant peoples habitually are 'a day late and a dollar short'. The main reason for managing time is just provide structure to one's life and in turn, peace of mind. Managing time is just something one does for one's own psyche, to make one's days easier.

The two indispensable keys to Time Management are: 1) the ability to set priorities; and 2) the ability to concentrate single-mindedly on one thing at a time. When thinking about Time Management, people tend to think of personal Time Management, loosely defined as managing their time to waste less time on doing the things they have to do so that they have more time to do things they want to do. Time Management is often thought of or presented as a set of Time Management will be more or organized, efficient and happier.

3. Academic Achievement

Academic Achievement can be defined as excellence in all academic disciplines, in the class as well as extracurricular activities. It includes excellence in sporting, behavior, confidence, communication skill, punctuality, assertiveness, art, culture and the like.

Academic Achievement generally refers to a child's performance in the academic areas (e.g., reading or language, art, maths, science and history). The definition could vary depending on a child's circumstance or situation.

Academic Achievement is the specified level of attainment or proficiency in academic work as evaluated by teachers or by standardized test or combination of both. Thus achievement refers to what a person has acquired after specific training or instruction has been imparted/ academic achievement can be assessed by tests, which are primarily designated to measure the effects of specific program of instruction or training. Academic stress is common among students because of many grounds. When facing difficult materials or subjects the students because of many grounds. When facing difficult materials or subjects the student level of concentration is higher leading to an increase in the unsatisfactory sensation. For instance, a student who is preparing for a test in algebra will battle more with numbers and formulas than a student preparing for a much easier test.

4. Time Management and Academic Achievement

It is important for a student to have effective strategies to manage his time to balance the conflicting demands of time for the study. Time Management skills are valuable for doing revision for examinations. Sometimes it may seem that there is not enough time to do everything that we need to. This can lead to a buildup of stress. When revising for examinations or during our final year when we have to combine the pressures of intensive study with finding time to apply for our task good management of our time can be particularly important. Once we have identification ways in which we can improve the management of our time, we can begin to adjust our routines and patterns of behavior to reduce any time-related stress in our lives.

5. Statement of the Problem

The statement of the problem is stated as “TIME MANAGEMENT AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT OF HIGHER SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS”.

6. Method of the Study

The method of the study depends upon the purpose and objectives of the study .

The present research is concerned about studying the Time Management and Academic Achievement and their interrelationship in their existing condition in the population; it is bound to follow ‘survey method’.

7. Tools Used in the Study

The tool prepared by the investigator with the help of supervisor was given to subject experts in the field of Psychology Studies. Based on the expert’s opinion some of the items of the tool were deleted and other necessary modifications were incorporated in the tool with the remaining statements a study was conducted among 81 higher secondary school students the collected data were standardized by and it was finalized.

It is a 5 point likert type scale. Out of 60 items 43 items were selected in Time Management. The Maximum and Minimum score is 215 and 43.

8. Sampling and Sampling Techniques

The population of the present study was Twelfth class students in Krishnagiri district. The data were collected from 81 students of Higher Secondary Students from six schools selected randomly.

9. Need for the Study

- 1) Scholarly literatures show that time management is one of the factors academic achievements among students.
- 2) Pehlivan (2013): There is significant positive correlation between time management and grade points average.
- 3) Misra & McKean (2000): There is a relation between time management and increased academic success.
- 4) Providing proper guidance in time management techniques can produce better academic achievement.

10. Objectives of the Study

To study whether there is any significant difference in Time Management and Academic Achievement with respect to the following variables:

- Gender
- Locality of the student

- Medium of Instruction
- Type of School Management
- Type of school

11. Hypotheses of the Study

There is no significant difference in Time Management and Academic Achievement with respect to the following variables :

- Gender
- Locality of the student
- Medium of Instruction
- Type of School Management
- Type of school

12. Operational Definitions

Time Management

Time Management is a set of principles, practices, skill, tool and systems that work together to help us to get more value out of our his/her time with the aim of improving the quality of our life. The most appropriate word which suites Time Management is self-management which helps us to keep stress to a maximum. Time is the scarcest resource and unless its management decides the success or the failure of an activity.

Academic Achievement

Academic Achievement is defined as the success of the student's in the field of education with the help of study. Academic Achievement can be defined as excellence in all academic disciplines, in the class as well as co-curricular activities. It includes excellences in sports, behavior, confidence, communication skills, punctuality, assertiveness, art, culture and the like.

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Time Management, and Academic Achievement for Entire Sample.

Variables	Mean	Standard Deviation	Mean Percentage
Time Management	136.11	9.35	63.3
Academic Achievement	68.17	11.88	68.17

From the Results shown in Table 1, it may be clear that the overall Mean value and Standard Deviation value of Time Management for the entire sample were 136.11 and 9.36 respectively. Mean value and Standard Deviation value of Academic Achievement for the entire samples were 68.17 and 11.88 respectively.

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Time Management, and Academic Achievement with respect to Gender

Variables	Male		Female		t-value	Level of significance
	Mean	S.D	Mean	S.D		
Time Management	135.12	9.788	137.51	8.521	2.859	P<0.01
Academic Achievement	68.34	13.024	67.92	10.066	0.386	P>0.05

From the Results shown in Table 2, it may be clear that the overall Mean value of Time Management of Male and Female were 135.12 and 137.51 respectively.

The results also indicate Mean value of Academic Achievement of Male and Female were 68.34 and 67.92.

The t-value in Table depicts that Male and Female differ significantly in the Time Management at 0.01 level. Further, it may also be found that the female students have more Time Management than male students.

The t-value in Table depicts that Male and Female did not differ significantly in the Academic Achievement at 0.05 level. There is no significant difference in Academic Achievement of male and female students.

Table 3: Mean, Standard Deviation and t-values of Time Management and Academic Achievement with respect to Locality

Variables	Rural		Urban		t-value	Level of significance
	Mean	S.D	Mean	S.D		
Time Management	136.16	10.097	136.05	8.422	0.137	P>0.05
Academic Achievement	69.94	11.782	66.10	11.684	3.68	P<0.01

From the Results shown in Table 3, it may be clear that the overall Mean value of Time Management of Rural and Urban students were 136.16 and 136.05 respectively.

The results also indicate Mean value of Academic Achievement of Rural and Urban students were 69.94 and 66.10.

The t-value in Table depicts that Rural and Urban students differ significantly in the Time Management at 0.05 level. Further, it may also be found that the Rural students have more Time Management than Urban students.

The t-value in Table depicts that Rural and Urban students did not differ significantly in the Academic Achievement at 0.01 level. Rural students have higher Academic Achievement than Urban students.

Table 4: Mean, Standard Deviation and t-values of Time Management and Academic Achievement with respect to the Medium of Instructions

Variables	Tamil		English		t-value	Level of significance
	Mean	S.D	Mean	S.D		
Time Management	135.92	8.556	136.28	10.027	0.427	P>0.05
Academic Achievement	64.82	10.107	71.19	12.553	6.267	P<0.01

From the Results shown in Table 4, it may be clear that the overall Mean value of Time Management of Tamil and English Medium students were 135.92 and 136.28 respectively.

The results also indicate Mean value of Academic Achievement of Tamil and English Medium students were 64.82 and 71.19.

The t-value in Table depicts that Tamil and English Medium students differ significantly in the Time Management at 0.05 level. Further, it may also be found that the English Medium students have more Time Management than Tamil Medium students.

The t-value in Table depicts that Tamil and English Medium students did not differ significantly in the Academic Achievement at 0.01 level. English medium students have better Academic Achievement than Tamil medium school students.

Table 5: Mean, Standard Deviation and t-values of Time Management and Academic Achievement with respect to Type of School Management

Variables	Government		Aided		Private		t-value	Level of significance	Groups Differed Significantly
	Mean	S.D	Mean	S.D	Mean	S.D			
Time Management	134.63	8.93	139.13	8.65	136	10.07	10.05	P<0.01	1&2, 2&3
Academic Achievement	64.38	9.46	69.53	10.46	73.81	14.31	32.37	P<0.01	1&2, 2&3, 1&3

From the Results shown in Table 5, it may be clear that the overall Mean value of Time Management of Government, Government Aided and Private school students were 134.63, 139.13 and 136 respectively.

The results also indicate Mean value of Academic Achievement of Government, Government Aided and Private school students were 64.38, 69.53 and 73.81.

The t-value in Table depicts that Government, Government Aided and Private school students differ significantly in the Time Management at 0.01 level. Further, it may also be found that the Government Aided school students have more Time Management than Government and Private school students.

The t-value in Table depicts that Government, Government Aided and Private school students did not differ significantly in the Academic Achievement at 0.01 level. Private school students have better Academic Achievement than Government and Aided school students.

Table 6: Mean, Standard Deviation and t-values of Time Management and Academic Achievement with respect to Type of School

Variables	Boys		Co-Education		Girls		F-ratio	Level of significance	Groups Differed Significantly
	Mean	S.D	Mean	S.D	Mean	S.D			
Time Management	133.3	9.11	136.16	9.63	138.16	8.53	10.75	P<0.01	1&2, 1&3
Academic Achievement	63.75	9.83	70.67	13.54	68.84	9.83	15.89	P<0.01	1&2, 1&3

From the Results shown in Table 6, it may be clear that the overall Mean value of Time Management of Boys, Co-Education and Girls school students were 133.30, 136.16 and 138.16 respectively.

The results also indicate Mean value of Academic Achievement of Boys, Co-Education and Girls school students were 63.75, 70.67 and 68.84.

The t-value in Table depicts that Boys, Co-Education and Girls school students differ significantly in the Time Management at 0.01 level. Further, it may also be found that the Girls school students have more Time Management than Boys and Co-Education school students.

The t-value in Table depicts that Boys, Co-Education and Girls school students did not differ significantly in the Academic Achievement at 0.01 level. Co-Education school students have more Academic Achievement than Boys and Girls school students.

13. Findings Related to Time Management

- 1) The male students have more Time Management than female students.
- 2) The rural students have more Time Management than urban students.
- 3) English medium students have more Time Management than Tamil medium students.
- 4) Private school students have more Time Management than Government, and Aided School Students.
- 5) Co-Education school students have more Time Management than students studying in Boys and Girls school.

14. Findings Related to Academic Achievement

- 1) There is no significant difference in Academic Achievement of male and female students.
- 2) Rural students have higher Academic Achievement than Urban students.
- 3) English medium students have better Academic Achievement than Tamil medium School students.
- 4) Private school students have better Academic Achievement than Government and Aided school students
- 5) Co-Education school students have more Academic Achievement than Boys and Girls school students.

15. Conclusion

Time Management correlates with Academic Achievement of the students. Therefore it is important to improve Time Management which will increase Academic Achievement. There is an urgent need to identify better ways for improve Academic Achievement and reduce Academic Stress among students. Hence it is necessary for all the stakeholders of education to enhance the Time Management behaviour of students to improve Academic Achievement.

16. Educational Implications

- 1) Time management is very important for every individual to be successful in academic career as well as in life. It may be cultivated and developed if found low among the higher secondary school students.
- 2) Time management is found to be essential skill for career success. It is a good skill to improve efficiency and effectiveness.
- 3) Poor time management may increase stress, so time management is necessary for academics as well as throughout the life.
- 4) Time management is an important factor for academic success of all students. Therefore effective time management strategies are essential to increase achievement.
- 5) Time management is an important factor for academic success for students at all levels of education. Some amount of it is vital to bring the best out of any individual, more of it is dangerous. Therefore strategies to increase Time management are essential in order to improve achievement.

17. Suggestions for Further Study

- 1) Similar study may be focused on various levels of education throughout the country.
- 2) Time management and academic stress can be studied in relation to some other variables like motivation, adjustment, underachievement, burn outs, etc. among students.
- 3) Time management can be studied in relation to some other variables like motivation, job satisfaction, burn outs, etc. among teachers.
- 4) Effectiveness of Time management strategies can be studied through experimental method.

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